

ISic2740

I.Sicily inscription 2740

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Entella

Place of origin (modern)

Rocca d'Entella

Provenance

Necropolis B, localita Petraro

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Contessa Entellina, Museo

Archeologico/Antiquarium Comunale di Entella, inventory E4334

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI339995

1. [τῶ — —]οῦ τῶ Νάνοῦ εἰμί.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644838

PHI 339995

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 47.1420

Dubois, Laurent 2008. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile. Tome II..
Geneva. At 84

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Seconde Giornate Internazionali di studi sull'area elima (Gibellina, 22-26 ottobre 1994). Atti. Pisa. pp. 1187-1202. At 1188 tav.CCXXXIII.1

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